

Drought resistance

Root growth and water extraction pattern of six rices in rainfed conditions

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In 1983 kharif we studied root growth and water extraction pattern of six rices grown in upland rainfed fields. Vertical rooting distributions of the varieties differed (Fig. 1).

Safri 17 had the highest root density (57 mg/cm³) in the top 10 cm of soil, and MW10 had the lowest (19 mg/cm³). Mahsuri, Usha, IR36, and Poorva were similar with intermediate density. Eighty-nine to 94% of roots were in the top 10 cm of soil, 4 to 9% were in the 10 to 20 cm layer, and the rest were 20 to 50 cm deep.

Figure 2 shows the water absorption patterns from flowering to maturity for Safri 17, Mahsuri, and Usha. The other varieties matured before rains ceased, preventing the study of their water extraction patterns.

Varietal differences in water extraction paralleled those of root growth. Root density in the 0 to 10 cm layer was highest for Safri 17, as was water extraction, which increased gradually with increasing depth to 45 cm – lowest depth measurement.

Five days after rains ceased, water extraction from the 5 to 45 cm soil layer was 1.6 mm/d for Safri 17, 0.8 for Mahsuri, and 0.8 for Usha. During the next 20 d, water extraction from the 5 to 15 cm layer diminished considerably, and extraction from 35 to 45 cm increased markedly.

A comparison of water extraction pattern (Fig. 2) and rooting pattern (Fig. 1) suggests that rooting density might not have been the sole determinant of water uptake. Soil water factors (soil water pressure and potential, and hydraulic conductivity) must also be considered. Five days after rains ceased, soil water

2. Water extraction pattern of 3 rice varieties, Raipur, India.

factors favored water uptake from the surface layers. Twenty days later, when surface soil had dried, the crops extracted water from the deeper, wetter layers. Figure 2 shows that rice varieties differ

in their ability to extract water from the deeper layers. Those differences can be exploited by choosing appropriate varieties for drought-prone upland environments. □

Deep water

Germination of seed from deep water varieties grown in deep water and field conditions

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Photoperiod-sensitive floating rices Jaladhi 1 and Jaladhi 2 were grown in

deep water and normal field conditions at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal. Weekly water level variations in two plots are in Figure 1.

The seeds were direct-seeded in wet soil (37-41% soil moisture) in late May. At harvest (Dec), the field had 25-30% soil moisture and the deep water plot had about 40 cm water. Seeds were thoroughly dried, cleaned, and stored in cloth bags.

Seed viability was monitored for 12 mo. The average germination percentage from two replications is in Figure 2.

Seeds had varying dormancies. Those from shallow water plots generally had poorer viability retention than those from deep water plots (Fig. 2). But, irrespective of variety, germination up to 4 mo. after harvest was slightly higher for seeds from the shallow water plot. Viability of seeds from such fields was highest in Apr, then abruptly decreased.

Seeds from the deep water plot maintained proper viability until Jul, after which viability decreased. They retained

more than 80% germination ability beyond 7 mo. No remarkable varietal difference in germination was recorded for seeds from either water regime.

In shallow water, many seeds of both varieties were underdeveloped, with high grain sterility and low grain filling. This may have been caused by lodging and drought at the grain ripening stage. Abnormal grain formation probably reduced nutrient supply to the grain, which may have reduced seed viability. Drought and lodging normally do not occur at grain filling under deep water conditions.

The viability of rice seeds generally is

controlled by genetic and environmental conditions. Our research emphasizes that, if high seed viability is to be maintained, multiplication of deep water rice seed should be done in native deep water environmental conditions rather than in lowland field conditions. □

1. Duration of crop growth phases and weekly variations in water level of 2 field conditions, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India.

2. Monthly changes in germination of seeds of 2 floating rice varieties from deep water and normal fields. Chinsurah, India.

Pest control and management DISEASES

Siratro, a new alternate host of *Thanatephorus cucumeris*

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Sheath blight (ShB) of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, imperfect state of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, has been a minor disease in Tamil Nadu. In Nov–Dec 1983, however, siratro *Macroptilium atropurpureum*, a fodder crop grown after rice, was completely defoliated. Dark brown sclerotia were

abundant on the dried leaves.

Infected plants were collected to isolate the causal organism. The fungus was identified as *R. solani*. The pathogenicity of the fungus was confirmed by artificial inoculation using mycelial bits from a culture or sclerotia collected from infected leaves of siratro. The first symptoms were 10 × 6 mm greenish grey, ellipsoidal spots on the leaves. Artificial inoculation on rice seedlings produced typical ShB symptoms in 7 d.

We compared the organism isolated from naturally infected rice seedlings

with that from siratro. The morphological characters were similar and the relationship was further confirmed by the two isolates' ability to anastomose.

The isolated organism was cross-inoculated on potted rice seedlings and siratro plants. In 5–7 d, both plants developed symptoms similar to those observed in the fields.

Our information indicates the potential of siratro as source of ShB inoculum. Feeding infected fodder to cattle will also disseminate the pathogen through cow dung. □